

Functional and Radiological Outcomes of Plate Osteosynthesis Fixation and Interlocking Nailing Fixation Following Fracture Shaft of the Humerus: A Comparative Follow-up Study

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Abstract:

Background: Fractures of the humeral shaft account for 1 to 3% of all fractures and are among the more common types of fractures.

Objectives: To compare the functional and radiological outcomes in patients with humeral shaft fractures treated with Plate Osteosynthesis versus those treated with Intramedullary Interlocking Nailing.

Methods: A prospective comparative study on the management of acute humeral shaft fractures was conducted in the Department of Orthopedics at the Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences, Puducherry. The study included two groups of participants: Group A, who underwent plate osteosynthesis, and Group B, who received antegrade intramedullary interlocking nailing.

Results: In a study of patients aged 21 to 69 years (mean age 37.7 years), 70.5% were male. The majority of fractures (65.38%) were caused by road traffic accidents, with 74.4% involving the right humerus. Subtype A2 was most common, with 51.3% of cases. Surgery occurred within a week for 90% of patients. Pre-operative radial nerve palsy was present in 3.84%, with all cases recovering. Post-operative complications included wound infections (4.2% plating, 3.3% nailing) and shoulder movement restrictions (16.7% nailing). The plating group showed superior shoulder outcomes ($p < 0.05$), though overall outcomes were similar between groups ($p > 0.05$). Radiologically, 70% of patients in the nailing group and 80% in the plating group achieved fracture union by 16 weeks. Non-union rates were higher in the nailing group (10%) compared to the plating group (4.16%).

Conclusion: Both the treatment methods achieved similar union rates; however, the interlocking nailing group had a higher incidence of secondary complications.

Keywords: Functional outcomes, Radiological outcomes, Plate Osteosynthesis Fixation, Interlocking Nailing Fixation, Fracture shaft of Humerus.

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Introduction

Fractures of the humeral shaft account for 1 to 3% of all fractures and are among the more common types of fractures.[1] These fractures typically result from high-energy trauma and are most frequently observed in the middle third of the shaft. Historically, humeral shaft fractures have been managed non-operatively using a hanging cast or brace.[2] Sarmiento et al.[3] Reported the use of a

plastic sleeve with early initiation of functional activity. However, non-operative treatment has certain drawbacks, including the need for prolonged immobilization in a cast or brace, which may extend up to six months, leading to significant morbidity.[4] Moreover, conservative management is not suitable for all humeral shaft fractures. Various conservative treatments are available, each

with specific indications. The coaptation splint is suitable for acute humeral shaft fractures with minimal shortening and short oblique or transverse fracture patterns, although it can cause irritation to the axilla and may slip.[5] The Velpeau bandage is appropriate for minimally displaced or undisplaced fractures that do not require reduction.[6] The hanging arm cast is indicated for displaced midshaft humeral fractures with shortening, particularly those with spiral or oblique patterns.[7] For the cast to be effective the patient must remain in an upright or semi-upright position at all times. Functional bracing, on the other hand, uses hydrostatic soft tissue compression to achieve and maintain fracture alignment while permitting motion of adjacent joints.[8] This method is typically applied one to two weeks after initial treatment with a hanging arm cast or coaptation splint.

In terms of surgical options, plate osteosynthesis, intramedullary nailing, and external fixation are available. Plate osteosynthesis is considered the gold standard for fixing humeral shaft fractures compared to other methods.[9,10] However, this technique requires extensive soft tissue dissection and carries the risk of complications due to the proximity of the radial nerve and the potential for mechanical failure in osteoporotic bones in elderly patients.

Intramedullary interlocking nailing is biomechanically a superior option because it functions as a load-sharing device, unlike plates, which are load bearing. Nails are subjected to smaller bending loads, making them less likely to fail due to fatigue. [11,12] Cortical osteopenia, which often occurs near the ends of plates, is rarely seen with intramedullary nails, thereby reducing the likelihood of refracture after implant removal. This method does not require extensive soft tissue dissection and provides stable fixation and rotational control. The procedure can be performed through either an antegrade or retrograde approach. Traditionally, closed intramedullary nailing for humeral shaft fractures has been indicated for patients with polytrauma, fractures with overlying burns, osteoporotic bones, pathological fractures, and segmental fractures.[13] The development of the interlocking nail system has significantly expanded these indications, allowing for the effective treatment of humeral shaft fractures with severe comminution or bone loss, while maintaining length and rotational alignment. External fixation, however, is typically reserved for the management of compound injuries and is not used as a definitive method of fixation.

Against this background, the aim of this study is to compare the functional and radiological outcomes in patients with humeral shaft fractures treated with Plate Osteosynthesis versus those treated with

Intramedullary Interlocking Nailing. The objectives are to evaluate and compare the results of these two treatment methods with respect to functional outcomes, as measured by the Constant shoulder score and Mayo elbow performance score, and radiological outcomes, assessed through fracture union on radiographs. Additionally, the study seeks to compare the incidence of complications such as surgical site infection, shoulder stiffness, and neurovascular injury between the two treatment approaches.

Materials and Methods

A prospective comparative study on the management of acute humeral shaft fractures was conducted in the Department of Orthopedics at the Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences, Puducherry. The study included two groups of participants: Group A, who underwent plate osteosynthesis, and Group B, who received antegrade intramedullary interlocking nailing. The study spanned nine years, from October 2008 to February 2017. The inclusion criteria for the study were acute fractures of the humeral shaft located 2 cm below the surgical neck and 3 cm above the olecranon fossa, closed diaphyseal humeral fractures less than one week old, multiple injuries, and participants over the age of 18. Exclusion criteria included open fractures, pathological fractures, polytrauma injuries, vascular injuries, and floating shoulder and elbow conditions.

Participants initially underwent evaluation following the Advanced Trauma Life Support (ATLS) protocol,[14] with fractures classified according to the AO classification system.[15] For initial immobilization, a U-slab was applied until the patient was deemed fit for surgery. All patients received appropriate clinical and radiological assessments before a decision was made to proceed with surgical intervention. Immediately after surgery, anteroposterior and lateral view X-rays were taken. Post-operative care included administering three doses of intravenous antibiotics, along with supportive oral analgesics and anti-inflammatory medications, depending on the patient's pain tolerance. Shoulder and elbow mobilization exercises were initiated on the second day post-surgery. Basic demographic data of all patients were recorded in a study proforma and maintained in Microsoft Excel.

Patients were followed up at regular intervals—6 weeks, 3 months, 6 months, and 9 months, with a maximum follow-up period of 9 months. X-rays were also taken during these follow-up visits. An independent observer, not involved in the study, assessed functional outcomes using the Constant Shoulder Score[16] and Mayo Elbow Performance Score [17] during each visit. Radiological

outcomes were evaluated based on radiographic evidence of union (number of cortex unions).

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Board. Written informed consent from the patients and inter-departmental permission were secured in accordance with hospital regulations. For data analysis, the information was entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS software version 25.0. Descriptive data for both groups were presented as frequencies and percentages. The Chi-Square test was used to identify associations between the groups and selected variables.

Results

In a study involving 166 patients with closed acute humeral shaft fractures requiring surgical intervention, treatment was administered through either interlocking nailing or plate osteosynthesis. Of the 105 patients treated with plate osteosynthesis, 57 (54.3%) were lost to follow-up by the end of the study. Similarly, of the 61 patients treated with interlocking nailing, 31 (50.8%) were lost to follow-up. After accounting for these dropouts, Group A consisted of 48 patients, and Group B had 30 patients. The average follow-up period for each patient was one year, ranging from 6 to 18 months.

The patients' ages ranged from 21 to 69 years, with a mean age of 37.7 years. The majority of patients were in the 31-40 years age group (45.7%), followed by those in the 21-30 years age group (25.7%). There were 55 male patients (70.5%) and 12 female patients (29.5%), with a similar gender distribution across both treatment groups. The majority of cases (65.38%) resulted from road traffic accidents, followed by 34.6% from accidental falls either at home or in the workplace. Additionally, the study found that 74.4% of the fractures involved the right humerus, with the left side being less commonly affected.

In the study, the distribution of AO subtypes among patients treated with Plate Osteosynthesis and Interlocking Nailing was as follows: For subtype A1, 7 patients were treated with Plate Osteosynthesis and 3 with Interlocking Nailing, making up 10 patients in total (12.8%). Subtype A2 had 24 patients treated with Plate Osteosynthesis and 16 with Interlocking Nailing, totalling 40 patients (51.3%). Subtype A3 included 11 patients treated with Plate Osteosynthesis and 9 with Interlocking Nailing, accounting for 20 patients (25.6%). For subtypes B1 and B2, there were 3 patients treated with Plate Osteosynthesis and 1 with Interlocking Nailing in each subtype, resulting in 4 patients for each (5.1% each).

In this study, 90% of patients underwent surgery within one week of injury. The delay in surgery for

the remaining 10% of patients (8 individuals) was due to factors such as uncontrolled blood sugar levels, head injuries with altered consciousness, and other comorbidities. Splintering at the fracture ends was observed in 6.3% of patients in the plating group and 13.3% of patients in the nailing group during reaming. Pre-operative radial nerve palsy was present in 3.84% of the patients. Additionally, 15 patients sustained other injuries, including fractures of long bones and head injuries. In two cases in Group A, where open reduction was performed, the radial nerve was explored to check its integrity. Post-operative radial nerve palsy occurred in three cases within the plating group, while no cases were observed in the nailing group. However, all patients with both pre-operative and post-operative nerve palsy fully recovered, indicating that these were neuropraxia-type injuries.

Superficial wound infections occurred in 4.2% of patients in the plating group and 3.3% in the nailing group, with all infections resolving within a few days of intravenous antibiotics. One case (2.1%) of deep wound infection was reported in the plating group, which was managed with wound washing and antibiotics, followed by monitoring until union. No deep wound infections were noted in the nailing group. Shoulder movement restrictions were observed in 16.7% of patients in the nailing group and 2.1% in the plating group. The shoulder restrictions in the nailing group were attributed to rotator cuff injury during nail entry and nail impingement on the rotator cuff. Elbow movements remained free and complete in all patients.

Bone marrow injection was administered in cases of delayed union, involving four patients in the nailing group and one in the plating group. Primary bone grafting was performed in two patients in the plating group who had splintering at the fracture site, while secondary bone grafting was necessary for two patients in each group who developed non-union. One patient in the nailing group with non-union underwent exchange nailing and reaming. Implant failure was observed in two patients in the plating group during the immediate follow-up period, and in one patient with delayed union. These patients underwent repeat plating with longer plates and bone grafting and were monitored until union. Three patients in the nailing group experienced failed nailing procedures due to reamer breakage in two cases and shantz pin breakage in one case. These patients were subsequently treated with plate osteosynthesis and followed until union. The mean duration of hospital stay was slightly longer in the nailing group, averaging 6.20 days, compared to 5.30 days in the plating group. The average duration of surgery was also longer in the nailing group at 115.16 minutes, compared to 95.72 minutes in the plating group.

At the final follow-up of the study, conducted at nine months, 27 out of 30 patients in the interlocking nail group achieved good to excellent outcomes. In comparison, 47 out of 48 patients in the plating group experienced similar results. This difference was statistically significant according to the chi-square test ($p < 0.05$), with the plating group showing superior shoulder movement compared to the nailing group. However, when considering overall outcomes, all patients in both the interlocking nail and plating groups achieved good to excellent results by the study's final follow-up. This difference in overall outcomes was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Both groups exhibited similar elbow movement capabilities.

Radiologically, 70% of patients in the interlocking nail group and 80% in the plating group showed signs of fracture union by or before 16 weeks. Delayed union was observed in five patients, who subsequently received additional bone marrow injections. Non-union occurred in 10% of cases in the interlocking nailing group. Of these, one patient was treated with closed exchange nailing and reaming, while the other two underwent bone grafting.

In the plating group, non-union was observed in 4.16% of cases, with both patients receiving bone grafting as a secondary procedure. Ultimately, all cases in both groups achieved fracture union.

Table 1: Comparison of functional outcomes between the study groups

	Plate Osteosynthesis				Interlocking Nailing				p value
	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	
Shoulder score (Constant and Murley)									
6 weeks	23	20	5	0	8	13	9	0	0.048
3 months	32	13	3	0	13	10	7	0	0.045
6 months	41	6	1	0	19	7	4	0	0.046
9 months	43	4	1	0	20	7	3	0	0.040
Elbow score (Mayo elbow performance score)									
6 weeks	43	5	0	0	22	8	0	0	0.609
3 months	46	2	0	0	26	4	0	0	0.139
6 months	47	1	0	0	28	2	0	0	0.305
9 months	47	1	0	0	28	2	0	0	0.305

Table 2: Comparison of radiological outcomes between the study groups

Duration	Procedure	No callus	Callus	One cortex	Two cortex	Three cortex	Four cortex	p value
6 weeks	Plate Osteosynthesis	41	7	0	0	0	0	0.163
	Interlocking Nailing	22	8	0	0	0	0	
3 months	Plate Osteosynthesis	12	2	10	9	8	7	0.297
	Interlocking Nailing	9	3	7	6	3	2	
6 months	Plate Osteosynthesis	0	0	2	2	3	41	0.314
	Interlocking Nailing	0	0	2	1	3	24	
9 months	Plate Osteosynthesis	0	0	0	0	5	43	0.694
	Interlocking Nailing	0	0	0	0	4	26	

Figure 1: Radiological and functional outcomes in a patient following right humeral shaft fracture and postoperative follow-up after plate osteosynthesis. Radiological outcome: Preoperative right humeral shaft fracture (A); Follow-up post-surgery on 3rd month and 9th month respectively (B, C). Functional outcome: After complete union (D, E & F)

Figure 2: Radiological and functional outcomes in a patient following left humeral shaft fracture and postoperative follow-up after plate osteosynthesis. Radiological outcome: Preoperative left humeral shaft fracture (A); immediate post-op (B); Fracture union at 8th month (C). Functional outcome: After complete union (D, E & F)

Figure 3: Radiological and functional outcomes in a patient following right humeral shaft fracture and postoperative follow-up after interlocking nailing. Radiological outcome: Preoperative right humeral shaft fracture (A); Immediate post-op (B); Union of fracture at 8th month post-surgery (C). Functional outcome: After complete union (D, E & F)

Figure 4: Radiological and functional outcomes in a patient following right humeral shaft fracture and postoperative follow-up after interlocking nailing. Radiological outcome: Preoperative right humeral

shaft fracture (A); Immediate post-op (B); Union of fracture at the 9th month post-surgery (C). Functional outcome: After complete union (D, E & F)

A. Implant failure secondary to non-union

B. Intra-op metallosis

C. Immediate post-op

D. Union at 7 months

Figure 5: Postop complications due to implant (plate) failure. A, Radiological image showing implant failure secondary to non-union; B, Intra-op picture showing metallosis i.e. deposition of metal debris in the adjacent soft tissues; C, Radiological image after corrective surgery i.e. immediate post-op; D, Union at 7 months

Discussion

The age distribution in this study highlights a higher incidence of trauma among younger age groups. A significant majority of the patients who sustained these fractures were males, with road traffic accidents being the most common cause of injury, accounting for approximately 65% of cases in both treatment groups. Regarding non-union, previous literature reports an incidence of 2% to 4% following plating.[18] In our study, the incidence of non-union in the plating group was 4.2%. For interlocking nails, the incidence of non-union reported in the literature ranges from 0% to 8%, while in our study, the incidence was observed to be 10%.

This study found no significant difference in the time required for fracture union between the two treatment groups. This result is consistent with the findings of Raghavendra et al.,[19] who also reported no significant difference in bony union between the plating and nailing groups in their series of 31 cases. The incidence of pre-operative radial nerve palsy in humeral shaft fractures generally ranges from 6% to 15%. In our series, the incidence was 3.8%, with all three affected cases fully recovering, a result comparable to those

reported by Schwab et al., [20] who observed incidences of 7% and 6.8%, respectively.

In the plating group, the incidence of postoperative radial nerve palsy is typically reported to be between 2% and 5%. In our study, three cases (6.25%) of postoperative radial nerve palsy were observed, all of which recovered completely, suggesting a neuropraxia type of injury. In contrast, various studies have reported the incidence of postoperative radial nerve palsy in the interlocking nail group to range from 2.6% to 14.3%. [21,22] notably, our series did not observe any cases of postoperative radial nerve palsy in the nailing group. Wound infection following plating has an incidence of 1% to 2% according to existing literature.[23] In our study, two cases (4.2%) in the plating group developed superficial infections, which resolved with antibiotics. There was one instance (2.1%) of deep wound infection in the plating group, which required wound irrigation and antibiotic treatment. The incidence of intraoperative comminution during the insertion of interlocking nails is reported to be between 7.7% and 10%. In our study, intraoperative comminution was observed in 13.33% of the cases in the nailing group.

In this study, shoulder pain was reported by 5 out of 30 patients (16.7%) in the nailing group. This finding is consistent with the study by Stannard et al., which reported mild to moderate shoulder pain in approximately 20% of patients. Similarly, Chapman et al.[24] Observed a significant reduction in shoulder movement in patients treated with nailing. The impairment of shoulder function in these cases may be attributed to impingement at the acromion, leading to restricted abduction, as well as the disruption of the rotator cuff during antegrade nailing.

Conclusion

In our study, there was no significant difference in the time required for fracture union between the two treatment methods. However, the incidence of infection was higher in the plating group compared to those treated with closed reduction and interlocking nailing. Patients in the nailing group experienced restricted shoulder movement, likely due to the prominent nail tip at the entry site and disruption of the rotator cuff. Complications were more common in the interlocking nail group, primarily related to poor shoulder function and pain. Although both treatment methods achieved similar union rates, the interlocking nailing group had a higher incidence of secondary complications. Therefore, interlocking nailing of the humerus may lead to impaired shoulder function and increased complications and should be selected with caution.

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